

**Notes—Forthcoming Energy and Climate Law
Quarterly—2021**

NON-STATE ACTORS AND ENVIRONMENTAL AND
CLIMATE ASSESSMENT

[High Court of Justice Queen's Bench Division
Planning Court
22 May 2020
Case No: CO/4498/2019]

Drax Power Limited, a gas operator and owner of Drax Power Station, aimed to construct and operate two gas-fired generating units in North Yorkshire (U.K.). In fact, gas-fired generating units, falling under the legislation of nationally significant infrastructure project ("NSIP"), are subject to deliverance of a development consent order ("DCO") by the Secretary of State for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy. Pursuant to the section 37 of the Planning Act 2008, on 29 May 2018, Drax Power Limited made duly an application for a DCO, in the prescribed form specifying the development to which it related and supported by the consultation report and any other relevant documents.

The application was accepted on 26 June 2018 in accordance with the section 55 of the Planning Act 2008. From this point forward, a panel was appointed to examine the application and, on 4 July 2019, released their report suggesting that the Secretary of State for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy withholds the grant of the consent for the development. The Secretary of State for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy did not follow the report's conclusion, hence chose to grant, on 4 October 2019, the development consent order, considering de minimis modifications. ClientEarth, an environmental law charity which object comprises the protection of the environment and human health for the public benefit, sought to challenge a decision made by the Secretary of State for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, by means of a judicial review,

before the High Court of Justice Queen's Bench Division Planning Court.

ClientEarth first asks the court to hold that the Secretary of State misinterpreted EN-1, in particular by rejecting the group's view that the NPS distinguishes between the need for energy NSIPs in general and the need for any proposed development in particular. Second, ClientEarth argued that COD requests for energy NSIPs for which a need has been identified in EN-1 should be assessed on the basis of whether it promotes the satisfaction of that need and that this contribution should carry significant weight.

With respect to ground 1, ClientEarth put forward elements of interpretation accepted by the Expert Group, notably that although EN-1 implied the need for energy NSIPs in general, the specific need for the proposed development should be taken into account in the light of the evidence presented during the review. In this regard, it was argued, with reference to paragraph 5.2.24, that the evidence mobilized showed that energy production was moving towards low-carbon sources, in line with the policy objective of EN-1 requiring the transition to a low-carbon economy over time, and that, as a result, the energy requirements of each NSIP should be continuously adapted to reflect the transition energy market. In opposing this argument, the judge had emphasized that the correct interpretation of a policy such as an NPS was an objective question of law and could not depend on the evidence that happened to be presented in a particular review. Accordingly, the judge rejected this interpretation and concluded on this point that the Secretary of State was quite right not to take this approach.

As to ground 2, the plaintiff argued that since the Secretary of State's decision did not take into account the panel's findings, the Secretary of State was obliged to provide the fullest justification and reasons. In this case too, the judge considers that the Secretary of State nevertheless gave legally adequate reasoning on each of them in DL 4.20. Accordingly, he was not required to give any further details that might enlighten a participant in the review, as the Secretary

of State had relied on the relevant passages of the EN-1 standard, which was explicit. In this respect, the judge considered it useful to reject this ground as well.

Ground 3 of the application was based on the manner in which the Secretary of State had treated the assessment of GHG emissions from the proposed development in relation to EN-1 and EN-2. In this connection, the judge stressed that in relation to DL 6.7, the Secretary of State had taken an approach in accordance with Article 104(7). Indeed, she did not need to assess GHG emissions against the emissions reduction targets, nor did those emissions constitute a reason for refusing to give consent. Here, the judge rejected this ground, holding that none of the policies treat GHG emissions as an irrelevant consideration in a COD application or as an inconvenience to which no weight can be given.

The statement in ground 4 focuses on ClientEarth's claim that the Secretary of State had breached her obligation under section 104(7) of the PA 2008 to balance the negative impact of the proposed development against its benefits. By merely repeating the assessment it had already made under s. 104(3), ClientEarth argued that the Secretary of State did not properly exercise her discretion on the issue raised by s. 104(7). This argument was rejected by the judge who held that the Secretary of State did not give more weight to GHG emissions in that he considered that there were no compelling reasons in this case to do so. In this regard, the judge noted that the Secretary of State simply insisted that there was no sufficiently convincing reason to give more weight to this issue. Accordingly, the Secretary of State's decision had necessarily weighed all the positive and negative effects of the proposal before concluding that the benefits outweighed the negative effects of the proposal.

In ground 5, ClientEarth states that the Secretary of State did not assess the proposal's conformity with the economic feasibility of CCS, which is one of the policy requirements for CBI under EN-1. In this regard, ClientEarth has indicated that the assumptions made by Drax regarding future prices in

the PCC assessment, contrary to what it has done elsewhere for the baseline scenario in the climate change analysis, may be relevant. On this point, the judge found that there was no need to defend this argument, which was completely without merit.

ClientEarth relies on ground 6 based on the Secretary of State's failure to comply with the requirements of Regulations 21 and 30 of the Infrastructure Planning Regulations 2017, which include a component on measures to monitor GHG emissions. The regulation requires the monitoring of any significant adverse environmental effects of a development project. On this point, the Judge indicated that the Secretary of State and of Drax were entitled to argue that the requirements and objectives of Regulation 21 had been met and that no substantial harm had been caused. The regime for monitoring significant adverse environmental effects is provided for in the 2012 regulations. Thus, in order to achieve decarbonization over time, GHG emissions will be monitored, recorded, validated and reported to the EA. The judge rejected this argument and noted that Drax Power provides detailed conclusions on environmental impacts in its proposal.

Ground 7 is drawn from a lengthy presentation. The UK's net carbon account target for 2050 was reduced on 27 June 2019 from 80% to 100% below the 1990 baseline level. This is referred to as the "net zero target". However, the panel mentioned that this change came after the review was completed and only one week before they submitted their report to the Secretary of State. As this was not the basis for the Group of Experts' review of the application and did not affect their final conclusions, the Group of Experts considered that the Secretary of State should take the issue into account in the planning review. On this ground, the judge rejected the applicant's arguments, considering that the applicant had not been able to prove that any relevant harm had been suffered as a result of the matters complained of.

As in the previous case, in Ground 8, ClientEarth argues that the Secretary of State failed to consider the issue of the time limitation that was

necessary to deal with GHG emissions from a development project after 2050. It is submitted that the Secretary of State could not authorize the project to operate after 2050 without considering appropriate offset and/or CCS requirements. Here, the Judge found that the Secretary of State took into account the situation up to 2050 and beyond when deciding in accordance with the policy of EN-1 and EN-2. Furthermore, the judge made it clear that the issue of regular review and adaptation of these policies could not be considered as part of the CDA process. On this basis, he rejected this ground.

In consideration of all of these reasons, the application for judicial review must be dismissed.

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